

CCUS

SCOPING PAPER

CARBON CAPTURE, UTILISATION & STORAGE

A NEFI Innovation Hub

NEFI – The Innovation Network for Industrial Transformation

NEFI – New Energy for Industry is an innovation network consisting of over 100 industry partners, 8 research partners, and 4 institutional partners. With 25 research and innovation projects dedicated to industrial transformation in Austria, an investment volume of nearly €100 million has been mobilised.

The goals of NEFI are:

- **Climate Neutrality** – Supplying selected sites with up to 100% renewable energy.
- **Value Creation and Location Security** – Promoting technology development and exports “Made in Austria”.
- **Industrial Resilience** – Ensuring energy supply, optimising processes, and improving infrastructure for Austrian industry.

The solutions developed within NEFI address 53% of the CO₂ emissions expected by 2040 and have the potential to generate an economic benefit of €2.2 billion. Additionally, by 2040, more than 25% of fossil energy imports could be avoided.

Achieving a climate-neutral industry by 2040 requires significant research and development efforts. Essential technologies are not yet fully developed, tested, or scalable to a sufficient extent. To bridge technological gaps and strategically drive innovations along realistic, scenario-based transformation pathways, six Innovation Hubs have been established.

NEFI Innovation Hubs

The NEFI Innovation Hubs are specialised networks led by renowned research institutions. Their goal is to initiate high-impact research and innovation projects that support the transition to a climate-neutral industry and position Austria as a technology leader in renewable energy and industrial innovation.

Both large corporations and small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs), as well as research institutions, are invited to participate in the Innovation Hubs.

NEFI Innovation Hubs: value proposition for partners

- ☑ Regular networking and information events: The NEFI Technology Talks present current technologies, trends, and developments.
- ☑ Support throughout the innovation process: From project idea to funding application and impact assessment.
- ☑ Dissemination of results: Effective communication and visibility.
- ☑ Access to state-of-the-art laboratory infrastructure.

The NEFI Innovation Hubs focus on the following key areas: CCUS, Circular Economy, CO₂-neutral Gases & Hydrogen, Electrification & Energy Efficiency, Flexibility, and Industrial Symbiosis. These topics have been identified as crucial for achieving industrial climate goals across different industries and scenarios ([NEFI Pathway to Industrial Decarbonisation](#) and [transform.industry - in German](#)).

1. Carbon Capture, Utilisation and Storage (CCUS) – Current developments and trends

Since 2023, Carbon Capture Utilisation and Storage (CCUS) has gained increasing importance at the national level and has become a stronger focus for both industrial initiatives and ministerial agendas. The **Carbon Management Strategy** ([Link - in German](#)) defines the key priorities in this area.

While Austria has made progress in the international comparison, it still lags significantly in infrastructure development and legislation. In contrast, North Sea neighboring countries are considerably more advanced in their CCUS activities.

The framework conditions for CCUS are largely shaped by EU regulations, including the integration of **Carbon Dioxide Removal (CDR) into the Emissions Trading System (ETS)**, the allocation of free certificates, and legal requirements.

Key Trends in CCUS are:

- (1) CCS in hard-to-abate sectors:** Carbon Capture and Storage (CCS) is increasingly being deployed in emission-intensive industries where decarbonisation is hardly feasible through other means.
- (2) CCU for biogenic emissions:** The utilisation of biogenic CO₂ for producing Sustainable Aviation Fuels (SAF) and other products is gaining importance, offering a sustainable pathway for Carbon Capture and Utilisation (CCU).
- (3) Carbon Dioxide Removal (CDR):** The capture and sequestration of biogenic CO₂ as a compensation measure for diffuse emission sources will play a crucial role. Whether the shrinking ETS certificate volume tightens more quickly or more slowly than industrial decarbonisation progresses will determine whether BECCS (Bioenergy with Carbon Capture and Storage) becomes the price-setting technology of the EU CO₂ price.
- (4) Energy efficiency in the CCUS/CDR value chain:** The abatement costs for greenhouse gases through CCUS and CDR are driven by energy prices. Therefore, energy efficiency plays a key role throughout the entire CCUS/CDR value chain.
- (5) Exploration of CO₂ storage potential and infrastructure development:** The assessment of geological storage potential and the development of the necessary infrastructure are in focus. This includes the planning of CO₂ hubs and transport solutions, addressing technical, legal, and economic requirements for such hubs. Potential locations and transport options – such as Danube shipping and rail – could serve as interim solutions until a pipeline network for larger volumes (1–2 Mt/a or more) becomes available. Despite Austria's possible geological CO₂ storage sites, as a landlocked country, it will rely on the connection to international infrastructure in the long term. Until cross-border connections become available within the next 10 years, alternative transport routes for approximately 1 Mt/a must be developed to provide CCS solutions for industry.

2. High-Potential Technologies and Innovations in Carbon Capture, Utilisation and Storage (CCUS)

Based on the general trends in the field of CCUS, the following high-potential technologies and innovations can be identified:

- (1) Efficient integration into production processes:** To improve the economic viability of carbon capture technologies, a significant increase in energy efficiency is required. A key approach is the seamless integration of these technologies into production processes to reduce overall energy demand.
- (2) Synergies between pre-combustion technologies and hydrogen production:** The combination of pre-combustion technologies, such as oxy-fuel combustion, with hydrogen production presents a promising but underexplored approach to enhancing CO₂ capture efficiency within the CCUS process and potentially fostering new product innovations.
- (3) Advancement of chemical-catalytic, electrochemical, and photochemical processes:** The utilisation of CO₂ through innovative chemical-catalytic, electrochemical, and photochemical processes opens up new value-creation opportunities and drives technological progress.
- (4) Mineral carbonation as a CCS option:** Advancing mineral carbonation offers a simple and practical method for permanently binding CO₂, presenting a viable and easily implementable CCS solution.

3. Main Research Questions in the field of Carbon Capture, Utilisation and Storage (CCUS)

As part of the NEFI Innovation Hub for Carbon Capture, Utilisation and Storage (CCUS), projects will be developed to address the following research questions:

- Technology development and improvement of the energy efficiency of capture and synthesis plants
- Identification of CO₂ storage potential in Austria
- How can CCUS facilities be integrated into Austria's energy and infrastructure system? This includes the implementation of demonstration and pilot projects as well as the integration into existing industrial sites.
- Analysis of techno-economic and ecological aspects, as well as studies on social acceptance, market models, legal frameworks, and their development

4. Out-of-Scope Topics and Collaborative Overlaps

The following topics and industries are outside the focus area of the Innovation Hub:

- Fossil emissions from non-hard-to-abate plants

Through cooperation and alignment between the NEFI Innovation Hubs, synergies can be leveraged, technological trends identified, and innovations accelerated.

The NEFI Innovation Hub for Carbon Capture, Utilisation and Storage (CCUS) expects overlaps with the following NEFI Innovation Hubs:

- Electrification & Energy Efficiency: Heat integration, overall system, integration of heat pumps in capture plants
- CO₂-Neutral Gases & Hydrogen: Hydrogen is required to produce valuable hydrocarbons through CCU (competition for usage)
- Industrial Symbiosis: Especially biogenic CO₂ can be used as a raw material for the chemical industry

5. Hub Co-Leads & Contact Persons

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This scoping paper was developed within the framework of the NEFI+ Innovation Lab of the FTI initiative “Transforming Industry”, funded by the Austrian Climate and Energy Fund and the federal states of Upper Austria and Styria.